

Eight unexplored facts about the human brain

What controversial questions do they raise in light of the evolution of human creativity?

von

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Abstract

As significant as the advances in evolutionary anthropology and brain research have been over the past few decades, they have not yet been sufficient to convincingly reveal *the nature* of human beings. However, given the development of human civilization, it seems so evident that the nature of human beings is linked to their extraordinary intelligence that it hardly needs further empirical confirmation.

It remains controversial whether humans merely possess a *greater intelligence* than the more intelligent animals, albeit considerably so, or whether their intelligence gives them a *special position* in the animal kingdom. With this core question unresolved, it also remained unclear whether humans are still subject to biological, i.e., *genetic evolution*, or whether, on the contrary, they have left this behind in order to pursue an independent, *predominantly cognitive* development of their civilization. In a word, despite all its technological and scientific advances, humans still do not know exactly who they are: are they still animals *dominated by instinct*, or a *radically higher evolutionary form* of intelligent life?

It therefore seems appropriate to link together some far-reaching facts from human history that all relate to the human brain. This direct confrontation may reveal anomalies that allow us to gain a deeper insight into the nature of human cognition. All eight undisputed facts about the human brain add up to a functional paradox that raises serious questions: A brain whose physical structure has remained constant for tens of thousands of years has enabled humanity to achieve rapid creative development in ever-shorter periods of time - something not observed in any other higher animal. *How is this possible?* - The following article summarizes several established but rarely integrated facts in order to question whether the cognitive uniqueness of humans can be explained by *specific neurophysiological brain structures*.

Keywords: human brain, cognitive evolution, creativity, evolutionary anthropology, neuroscience, cultural acceleration, brain paradox, association cortex

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Why a new perspective on the human brain is necessary

It would be very strange if the current status quo remained unchallenged: Humanity has proven capable of constructing towering, highly complex particle accelerators that consume as much energy as small towns, of using molecular scissors to repair and optimize our invisible genetic code, and of deciphering ancient texts from charred parchment scrolls found in Pompeii – yet it still has not understood what essentially defines humanity, nor the decisive role it plays in cosmic evolution.

After all, evolutionary anthropology has made tremendous progress over the last 150 years: both paleontological and paleogenetic evidence has confirmed Darwin's hypothesis that the earliest human population originated solely in Africa, meaning that humans did not evolve in multiple regions. Furthermore, molecular genetics has shown that the genetic material of humans and great apes is more than 98% identical. Humans and great apes are therefore extremely closely related in biological terms; apparently, only a small difference in mutation can trigger a large difference in cognition. The genetic differences between all humans are even smaller, so that all physical differences, which sometimes appear serious, are *by no means substantial in nature*, but are merely due to the phenotypes of a single genotype. Even the sometimes astonishing differences in intelligence among humans, their *extremely different talents* for language, mathematics, music, or the visual arts, are not based on fundamentally different, decisive genes, but are merely due to allele variants – i.e., specific gene variants on a chromosome – and are therefore also *phenotypic* in nature.

This makes *four historical* facts concerning the human brain all the more challenging—initially from a *phenomenological* perspective – which have been known for some time but, to my knowledge, have never been analyzed in terms of their implicit significance: What does it mean for the nature of human beings if their brains have not undergone *any substantial genetic changes* since their emergence – yet still enable all of humanity's creative leaps in culture and civilization *with the same brain structures as animals*?

Four external, historical-empirical facts about the human brain

The following four fundamental facts about the phenomenology of the human brain must be considered in relation to each other:

1. It has been confirmed that the human brain has remained *biologically constant* since its growth ended 200,000 years ago (Bruner et al. 2014, Hawks 2011). (Its volume of around 1,400 cc has even decreased by approximately 100 cc since the emergence of agriculture 12,000 years ago, without any reduction in its performance since then – quite the contrary, in fact. Consequently, a *purely gradual* increase in cognitive ability – *even* with a *reduced* brain – cannot possibly lead to the subsequent creative explosion of civilization.)
2. As paleogenetic research has been able to prove in many ways: around 150,000 years ago, human populations separated from each other for a long time – so that globally, *no further improvement of their brains* could take place *through selection* (Prüfer et al. 2021/24, Stringer 2012) (We do know of *regional* adaptations in terms of their physique, but the human brain was not substantially altered at any point because, as *point four* will show, it could not be genetically altered.)
3. Colonialist and imperialist encounters have revealed the *cognitive equality of all humans at all times*: For people of every ethnicity on earth, no matter how many millennia they had been distant from developed culture and science, no matter how low or lowest their social class, proved themselves capable, with sufficient education and training, of learning and applying any body of knowledge that had been attained; they also showed no differences in aptitude compared to highly cultivated people.
4. From the diamond engravings on ochre in the Blombos Cave 77,000 years ago, to metallurgy 10,000 years ago, writing 5,500 years ago, and the heliocentric world view 500 years ago, to the decoding of DNA and the discovery of the Big Bang in the 20th century, humanity has undergone a magnificent creative development. This accelerating cognitive development does not consist solely of purely gradual cumulative learning and experience processes, but above all shows *creative tipping points* that could neither be derived from previous stages of cognition nor calculated purely logically.

Ad 2.: This cognitive development has always been *too rapid and too specific* for genetically and randomly expressed brain structures to have been able to follow it. The frequently claimed co-evolution of genes and culture – originally the interaction only between species – turns out to be,

among other things, a traditionalist auxiliary construct for this reason (Richerson & Boyd 2005, Henrich 2016).

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Interim result I

The paradox of brain constancy

If all this is true, doesn't it raise some serious questions? Let's first summarize the implications of these four basic facts about the human brain:

In animal evolution, we see – especially in the evolution of mammals – that new species become more intelligent when, for example, the neocortex becomes larger. If a species does not undergo fundamental changes over millions of years – such as elephants, orcas, and great apes – then they largely display the same level of cognition. In the direct predecessor of Homo sapiens, Homo erectus, we can track its brain growth over two million years quite well and, in parallel, a strikingly slow increase in cognition in qualitative stages.

Strikingly, the *four facts listed about the human brain* reveal exactly the opposite: brain growth in Homo erectus stopped around 200,000 years ago, and the archaic Homo sapiens that emerged from it retained this brain unchanged – *but paradoxically, it was still able to continuously increase its cognitive performance*. However, this did not happen gradually and continuously from the outset, but rather extremely slowly over the following 200,000 years, albeit in creative stages. From the emergence of agriculture 12,000 years ago, brain volume was reduced again by around 100 cc, but paradoxically, cognitive development accelerated from then on in stages from millennium to millennium, then from century to century, to undergo a permanent revolution in the present.

How are these *paradoxical phenomena* possible? What does this say about the systemic nature of the brain: if it does not change, but still enables ever higher levels of cognition? How can an unchanging brain accelerate its cognitive development more and more? Can it still be claimed that humans merely possess a *quantitatively determined* – albeit considerably greater – *level of intelligence* than the most intelligent animal?

However, these four external facts allow us to formulate an *initial, fundamental hypothesis* about the human brain:

If the human brain, as long as it exists, remains the same in terms of its specific structure, undergoes no significant changes, but nevertheless made

all the cognitive achievements of civilization possible, then these two indisputable facts combined mean something unprecedented: For the first time, biological evolution produced a brain that, thanks to its specific characteristics, is not bound by specific environmental requirements. Put positively, this means that the human brain – a complex system of information processing – is capable, like the complex system of biological evolution itself, of finding a sophisticated, creative response to any rapidly changing challenge posed by the environment. In a nutshell: *the human brain does not have specifically limited cognition, but rather the mere procedural potential for arbitrary cognitive development in creative stages.*

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Four neurobiological facts about the internal structure of the human brain

Perhaps we can begin to understand the reasons for this biological transformation once we take a look at the basic facts regarding the neural interior of the human brain. In addition, we must note the following regarding the structure of the human brain:

1. Neurophysiologically and architecturally, the human brain does not differ fundamentally from the brains of great apes – and even more amazing (Bruner et al. 2020, Hublin et al. 2015/18):
2. The only difference is a significantly larger number of neurons – and even more amazing (Herculano-Houzel 2016):
3. Especially in the association cortex – several brain regions for higher cognition – which has no specialization, their number increased and existing information is processed intracortically with largely identical neurons.
4. All pattern processes exhibit the characteristics of a complex system – because all elementary components of the brain, such as neurons, dendrites, and synapses, have an indeterminate character – and therefore cannot possibly be causal-logical in nature.

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Interim result II The neurobiologically complementary paradox

This means that the brain – both human and mammalian – is by no means composed of unambiguous, absolutely determinable components, nor is it

a mechanically determined and formally logical system, as it is still mostly treated: it has an unpredictably complex character – by no means exactly calculable or merely very complicated. Its interacting information patterns are probabilistic in nature, its processes are self-regulating and self-organizing at their core – meaning they are not caused – and higher forms of cognition can only be gained through processual evolution. Above all, creative achievements only become possible when the interaction of bifurcational – that is, branching – variants enables chaos-like original attractors – these are fixed states of attraction.

Accordingly, no particularly effective circuit diagrams, algorithms, or networks can be responsible for the astonishing creative leaps humans have made in their development. Perhaps this is due to very specific neurophysiological structures that have been added over the two million years of *Homo erectus*' cerebral enlargement? In fact, empirical brain research has been desperately searching for extraordinary brain structures, unique neuron types, or unusual neuron layer structures in humans over the last few decades – with no results. In terms of both general brain structure and cell types, as well as specific brain regions and areas, no significant differences are apparent when compared to the brains of great apes known to us. Paleogenetics also sought to find genes related to the brain that made a difference, especially in comparison with the Neanderthal genome decoded by Pääbo. Although some variants were found, they were all within the phenotypic spectrum. Even more clearly: Neanderthal-typical genes relating to the brain were even transferred to *Homo sapiens* during the Cro-Magnon period – but, significantly, were eliminated again in subsequent human generations.

After all this, what differences remain between the brains of great apes and those of *Homo sapiens*? At least two, which evolutionary anthropology and brain research should focus on more than before. First, the human brain grew disproportionately large, with an encephalization quotient of 5–7, and with it the number of neurons grew exponentially, since human neurons are also quite small and tightly packed, yet well insulated. Secondly, however, the number of neurons did not increase evenly in all parts of the brain, but mainly in the association cortex. The enlargement of the cerebrum mainly affected the association cortex, which increased from 50% in great apes to up to 80% in humans. What can be deduced from these two facts? Firstly, the fact that no new, extraordinary brain structures have developed means that all of humanity's magnificent and constantly evolving cognitive abilities must primarily be derived purely procedurally from complex processes involving similar, because unspecific, neurons in the association cortex. However, since great apes already performed their higher cognitive functions primarily by means of their equally large association cortex, the

following suspicion arises: from the complex processes of neural patterns, which could evolve arbitrarily creative leaps purely procedurally – i.e., independently of structure – an additional system state could occur in humans that is unknown in animals. Otherwise, there are no known viable possibilities to explain the creative development of cognition, whose complex processes, using the same, unspecific neurons, take on a quasi-autonomous character.

Instead of this knowledge reducing the mystery of the human brain, the mystery now seems even greater. What is the inevitable conclusion if science takes these eight universally confirmed facts seriously and puts them into context?

A merely gradually larger animal brain – because neurophysiologically, the human brain is nothing more than that – also remains constant. Nevertheless, it masters ever higher cognitive performances in ever shorter periods of time, overcoming creative stages; moreover, this cognitive development is accelerating noticeably. – Something very decisive must have happened to this brain, otherwise it could not possibly exhibit these paradoxical phenomena. In order to resolve these *paradoxes*, should we not ask ourselves some disturbing questions?

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A suspicion

Only a procedural system change remains to resolve the existing paradoxes

If the human brain – because it is known to be subject to stasis, i.e., stagnation – does not originally receive any additional neurophysiological structures, can it still function in a mechanically determined manner?

An electronic network *that calculates with absolute precision* – no matter how complicated it may be – does not produce unpredictable creative results, but at best more complicated variants and previously undiscovered logical implications.

Does this not raise the following questions: Could the secret of its enhanced cognitive development lie *primarily* in the *complexity* of exquisite neural *processes*?

Isn't this solution reinforced by the fact that the human brain has *exactly the same components* as the brains of higher animals (neurons, dendrites – the tree-like connections to the neurons – synapses – the contact points –

axons – the extensions of the neurons – and *structures* of the five brain regions)?

This analysis is reinforced by the only predominantly quantitative difference between the human brain and the animal brain, namely that the volume of the human association cortex increased from 50% to a staggering 80% – and with it, the number of neurons grew exponentially. This is because the neurons of the association cortex, with their probabilistic patterns, predominantly do not have a characteristic form, but are rather nonspecific in nature and primarily process intracortically among themselves. Doesn't this fundamental fact of brain research confirm the suspicion pursued here: All high, higher, but above all creative cognitive performances seem to be based on complex neural processes that have not yet been experimentally researched.

In that case, the only remaining explanation for the difference in quality is a peculiar tipping point that a significantly more complex – because exponentially enhanced – neural system could reach, thereby making the creative potential of a human brain plausible.

Summary

First of all, it was necessary to acknowledge the phenomenon of the external paradox of the enduring constancy of the human brain in contrast to the seemingly unlimited creative development of human history; internally, this phenomenon corresponds strikingly with the neurophysiological paradox of an animal brain that has only gradually increased in size significantly and, as the human brain – without additional, original, or other structures – makes purely procedural leaps in cognition.

Recognized research results prove that the human brain does not, by any means, produce original neurophysiological structures due to genetic evolution that could explain its extraordinary cognitive development and creative leaps. A co-evolution of genes and culture, advocated for the sake of continuity, must – when viewed critically – be rejected due to the categorical discrepancy between the duration of evolution and the random nature of genes on the one hand, and the speed and purposefulness of culture on the other.

Under these circumstances, is it so far-fetched to investigate the inevitably order-creating properties of hypercomplex processes of an increased flood of neural patterns as a new research approach? Perhaps their patterns of

order reach a critical threshold that could still explain the unpredictable leaps in the cognitive development of humanity with the same brain.

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